

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF AGRO-ECO PARKS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRO-ECO TOURISM

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Abstract

With the continuous development of society and the continuous improvement of people's living standards, leisure agricultural tourism based on agricultural production has gradually become popular. Which takes agricultural landscape, agricultural experience and agricultural product shopping as content. Leisure agricultural tourist attractions have emerged. At present, some agro-eco tourism projects are reconstruction or transformation projects, which are the recreational transformation of the original base for traditional agricultural projects in order to survive and seek market stimulation. However, due to the unscientific planning of the basic system, the low level of operation and management, and the lack of a scientific theoretical system for demonstration during the transformation process, the planning and transformation of the agro-eco tourism project have not been promoted. The project industry development has not been improved. Therefore, under the support of the concept of circular economy agro-eco parks technology to carry out the planning and analysis of agro-eco tourism tourist attractions, and combines the experiments to analyses the effectiveness of this method. From the research point of view, it can be known that the agro-eco tourism scenic area planning method constructed in this paper has certain effects.

Keywords: agro-eco tourism, ecological economy, sustainable agriculture, eco-agriculture, agro-eco parks and agro-ecotourism marketing.

Introduction

Agro-eco tourism is a type of tourism under the background of rural ecological environment. Moreover, it uses ecological agriculture and rural characteristic culture as its resources, applies aesthetics, ecology, economics principles, and sustainable development theories, uses human resources and natural resources to develop agro-eco tourism, and plans and constructs the rural environment in accordance with tourism environmental standards. At the same time, it takes eco-tourism as the main body, integrating agricultural production, the application of new agricultural technology, and tourist participation in sightseeing. In addition, it promotes the construction of ecological agriculture, the scientific and technological operation of agriculture, the exhibition of agronomic products, the promotion of agricultural and sideline products, and the good development of the rural ecological environment, so that tourists can feel agricultural modernization and rural ecologicalisation (Flachs and Richards 2018). Agro-eco tourism is based on the rural ecological environment, farmland work, pastoral style, agro-eco tourism production content and rural humanities. The importance of modernization is the achievements in the field of science and knowledge, faster growth of mechanization and growth, the explanation of social life, the appearance of balanced outlook in every walk of life. Through overall planning, layout, process design and a series of supporting facilities and services, it provides people with sightseeing, travel, and recuperation services. In addition, through tourist experience and participation in rural characteristic folk life, seasonal fruit and vegetable field visits and picking, and viewing of characteristic flowers and plants under intelligent technology, it combines fun and education to help people

understand modern agriculture and increase agricultural knowledge. Eco-agricultural tourism is committed to integrating the economic functions of eco-agricultural production with the socio-economic functions of eco-tourism, and strengthening the economic functions of eco-agriculture, so as to achieve the goal of protecting the environment and promoting ecological sustainable development. At the same time, it combines ecological agriculture and ecological tourism to promote economic growth, social progress, and ecological stability.

The development of agro-eco tourism mainly relies on local agro-eco tourism resources. Among them, natural resources and human resources reflect the local natural scenery and cultural customs, which are extremely attractive to tourists. As an attractive condition for agro-eco tourism, these tourism resources can be used to develop eco-tourism, and these resources have the characteristics of recycling or renewable. In addition, eco-agricultural tourism is developed based on tourists' 'clothing, food, housing, and transportation', and consumes relatively few natural resources. The eco-agriculture is a number of associated systems of connected system of farming practice which are preserving or educating the status of efficiency of soil, organization at the same period reducing damaging ecological effects. Ecological farming provides healthy agriculture and nutritious eating for yesterday and today by safeguarding soil, moisture, and weather, trying to promote bio-diversity, and attempting to avoid the use of chemical inputs or genetic modification. Recycling is an integral part of a circular economy, but should be regarded only as there are no other choices for re-use, re-manufacture, or fix. This really is the fundamental principle of the waste management hierarchy, that takes precedence most efficient waste management solutions.

The main input is human resources, and the human resources provided to tourists have the characteristics of recycling and conform to the concept of sustainable development. Therefore, the development of eco-agricultural tourism is consistent with the green development concept of sustainable development currently required by our country. Agro-eco tourism also conforms to the characteristics of low energy consumption, low emission, resource saving, and sustainable development, and fully embodies the green development concept of sustainable development.

Related work

Agro-eco tourism started early in some developed countries and has become an important part of the tourism industry in many countries. Its agro-eco tourism revenue accounts for more than 20% of the overall tourism revenue (Park and Oh, 2018). Agro-eco tourism mainly focuses on two development methods abroad (Alphey and Bonsall, 2018). A type of vacation that focuses on leisure viewing functions and belongs to the viewing type. This type of agro-eco tourism is more popular in Central and Eastern European countries, mainly including Hungary, Finland and other places. Another way of agro-eco tourism is personal contact with farmland, which is participatory vacation. In this mode, tourists want to experience farming by themselves, pick food by themselves, experience the fun of the countryside during busy farming, and watch the countryside scenery. It is mainly popular in Japan, the United States and other places. Ecological farming is the most respectful of wildlife, as it produces lower pollution of aerosols, it produces less carbon dioxide, it prevents the greenhouse effect, it doesn't generate polluting waste and helps make energy savings since in the crop cultivation and in the production of the products it takes advantage. Tourists who choose agro-eco tourism are mostly people in the city who have received higher education and have certain economic conditions. Through agro-eco tourism, they release their work pressure in the beautiful countryside, invest in the slow-paced rural pastoral life from the high-pressure working environment, and look for the natural cultural atmosphere brought by nature (Marcis et al., 2019). Up to now, many foreign countries have used their own scientific and technological advantages to introduce intelligence and technology into agro-eco tourism to pursue high-tech and high value-added goals, and to build a modern agricultural science and technology park as a carrier to maximise agricultural productivity (Mueller et al., 2017).

Some regions are committed to comprehensive development and utilisation of limited land, creating multi-functional high-tech agricultural parks such as ornamental leisure and foreign exchange earnings. At

the same time, Singapore's agricultural park actively invests in infrastructure to increase the entertainment of the park. Moreover, it has carefully distributed the corridor into a characteristic agricultural ecological corridor with tourism characteristics and can provide fresh agricultural products to form a multi-functional agro-eco tourism system (Turner et al. 2019). In some countries, agricultural science and technology parks use a well-established team of experts and a large number of science and technology practitioners to manage (Adama et al., 2018). The nature of the farms in each garden in the agricultural sightseeing garden system designed by Duan et al. (2019) is different, such as chicken farms, fish farms (export ornamental fish), mushroom gardens, bean sprouts farms, and vegetable gardens. These farms of various natures provide sophisticated agricultural technology for global agricultural investors and employ a large number of experts and scholars to promote agricultural technology. For example, Singapore's high-tech agricultural gardens have formed a complete urban agricultural system, and have achieved very good economic and social benefits.

The generic model

Developing an agro-eco tourism estate begins by using the basic strategies of agro-eco parks regarding site selection and development, building standards, infrastructure, and management. The opportunity for profitable by-product flows between tenants is particularly high with the biomass, energy, and water intensive companies in food processing. The recruitment for an agro-park focuses on the cluster of companies that support sustainable farming, helping farmers and agribusiness realize several basic objectives:

- Preserve and restore traditional farming practices that are ecologically sound.
- Support the transition from petrochemical-based industrialized farming to an ecologically-based model.
- Preserve and restore rural lands and water systems, avoiding further degradation.
- Preserve and renew the economies and societies of rural communities.

Achieving these objectives of sustainable agriculture calls for a very different support system than the present agribusiness suppliers of petrochemically-derived fertilizers and pesticides, heavy farm equipment and international commodity marketing. Although agro-eco parks are created very few in modern times, their role in agro-eco tourism and sustainable economic development in general is significant. The marketing research conducted in this field allowed to come to the following conclusions (Scheme 1).

Schema 1. Production and consumption in agroecotourism

The support system for sustainable farming includes several basic types of firms and agencies which may be recruited as tenants of an agro-eco tourism estate:

- Suppliers of equipment, energy, materials, and services to farmers;
- Food processing and distribution firms;
- Firms utilizing by-products from any part of the system.
- Intensive food production located in or near an agro-estate, particularly as landscaping, greenhouses and aquaculture ponds.

Thus, at present, some agri-ecotourism projects are reconstruction or transformation projects, which are the recreational transformation of the original base for traditional agricultural projects in order to survive and find incentives for the market. However, due to the non-scientific planning of the basic system, the low level of operation and management, and the lack of a scientific and theoretical system to demonstrate in the transformation process, the planning and transformation of the agri-ecotourism project has not been properly developed. Therefore, with the support of the concept of circular economy agro-eco-parks, planning and analysis of agro-ecotourism tourist attractions are carried out, as well as experiments to analyze the effectiveness of this method are combined.

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